

Studies on Metavanadate-Hydrofluoric Acid Systems

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A variety of complex oxyfluorides, all being derived from either the (a) oxytrifluoride, VOF_3 ; or from (b) the still unknown dioxyfluoride, VO_2F , have been described in literature¹. Among them typical members are :

Large number of more complex compounds of doubtful individuality have also been described².

The present authors have studied $\text{NH}_4\text{VO}_3\text{-HF}$ and $\text{KVO}_3\text{-HF}$ systems at various concentrations through conductometric, thermometric and potentiometric titrations and found three breaks in the molar ratios 1 : 0.5; 1 : 2; 1 : 3 of $\text{VO}^{-3} : \text{HF}$. These results are, in accord with our previous work³, where, from the colorimetric studies of metavanadate-hydrofluoric acid system, it has been shown that the above two react with the production of maximum colour at $\text{VO}^{-3} : \text{HF} = 1 : 0.5$ and minimum colour (in concentrated solution of reactants) at about 1 : 3.2.

By evaporating mixtures of (i) NH_4VO_3 with HF; (ii) KVO_3 with HF and (iii) NaVO_3 with HF in vacuum and at room temperature, the present authors have been able to isolate several compounds, the analytical details of the filterpressed products have been shown in Table 1.

Most of these compounds isolated from the above mixtures are unstable in air but stable only in dry cold atmosphere.

By evaporating mixtures of metal carbonates, vanadium pentoxide and excess hydrofluoric acid on water bath, the compounds, viz. $\text{Ni}[\text{HVO}_2\text{F}_3]_2 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Cu}[\text{HVO}_2\text{F}_3]_2 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ have been isolated. $\text{Ni}[\text{HVO}_2\text{F}_3]_2 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni 11.27, V 19.59, F 21.90 per cent. Found Ni 12.04, V 18.98, F 21.36%. $\text{Cu}[\text{HVO}_2\text{F}_3]_2 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu 12.52, V 20.10, F 22.47%. Found Cu 12.46, V 19.95, F 23.15%.

1. N. V. Sidgwick. The Chemical Elements and their Compounds, Vol. 1, p. 817, Oxford University Press, London (1962).
2. J. W. Mellor. A Comprehensive Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry, Vol. IX, pp. 796-802, Longmans, Green and Co. Ltd., London (1960).
3. A. K. Sengupta, *Z. anorg. allg. Chem.*, 1960, **304**, 332.

The titration data, as well as, the isolation of the above compounds may be explained through the successive formation of the following ionic species, viz., $HV_{10}O_{28}^{5-}$, $VO_2F_2^-$, $HVO_2F_3^-$, by reaction of a vanadate with hydrofluoric acid.

TABLE 1

Analytical data of the filter-pressed products obtained through the reactions of MVO_3 (where $M = NH_4, K, Na$) with HF.

Experimental				Approximate Ratio	Probable Compositions
$NH_4VO_3 : HF$	%N	%V	%F	N : V : F	
1 : 0.5	7.03	40.75	—	0.6 : 1	$(NH_4)_6V_{10}O_{28}.XH_2O$
1 : 2	13.06*	32.30	30.40	1.5 : 1 : 2.5	$(NH_4)_3V_2O_4F_5.XH_2O$
„	9.66	35.26	26.11	1 : 1 : 2	$NH_4VO_2F_2.XH_2O$
1 : 3	9.84	35.75	26.64	1 : 1 : 2	$NH_4VO_2F_2.XH_2O$
$KVO_3 : HF$	%K	%V	%F	K : V : F	
1 : 0.5	16.96	36.63	—	0.6 : 1	$K_6V_{10}O_{28}.XH_2O$
1 : 2	26.72	22.36	20.67	1.5 : 1 : 2.5	$K_3V_2O_4F_5.XH_2O$
1 : 3 (a)	27.20	22.05	21.01	1.5 : 1 : 2.5	$K_3V_2O_4F_5.XH_2O$
(b)	—	19.65	24.46	- : 1 : 3	$K_3VO_2F_3.XH_2O$
$NaVO_3 : HF$	%Na	%V	%F	Na : V : F	
1 : 2**	11.58	23.91	18.69	1 : 1 : 2	$NaVO_2F_2.XH_2O$
1 : 3	15.35	30.54	24.46	1 : 1 : 2	$NaVO_2F_2.XH_2O$

* cold condition and with alcohol

(a) 1st crop of crystals

(b) 2nd crop of crystals

** 3rd crop of crystals (No pure compounds were obtained in the 1st. and 2nd. crop of crystals).

By adding barium chloride to the mixture of NH_4VO_3 and HF in the ratios of 1 : 2 and 1 : 3, $BaVO_2F_3$ has been isolated from dilute solution of reactants, but from the concentrated solutions $BaHV_2O_4F_5$ contaminated with a little amount of barium fluoride was obtained. It, therefore, remains to be proved whether the substances having $V_2O_4F_5^{3-}$ group are salts containing $VO_2F_2^-$ and $VO_2F_3^{2-}$ ions as suggested by the precipitation⁴ of $BaVO_2F_3$ on adding a soluble barium salt to a solution of $K_3V_2O_4F_5$, or, a condensation product containing the discrete ion $V_2O_4F_5^{3-}$.

Further work is in progress.

Sincere thanks of the authors are due to the authorities of C.S.I.R. for awarding a Junior Research Fellowship to one of them (B.B.B.).

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Received November 8, 1968.